

Task 4.4A (Subtask 4): Update and Extend the RADx Data Hub Metadata Schema

Technical Report

Owner: Stanford University

Revision History

Date (YYYY-MM-DD)	Version Number	Revision Reviewed / Approved By	Brief Description of Change
Jun 24, 2025	v1	Stanford University team	First version
Jun 26, 2025	v2	Stanford University team	Minor improvements

Purpose

This technical report outlines the development and implementation of an updated metadata schema for the RADx Data Hub, addressing limitations in the original metadata schemas. The updated data file metadata schema enhances metadata coverage, streamlines structural design, and eliminates redundant or unused fields. In parallel, a new study metadata schema has been created to standardize and enhance the reusability of study-level metadata. This work corresponds to subtask 4, *Update and Extend the RADx Data Hub Metadata Schema*, under task 4.4A, *Evaluate and Improve Metadata Quality and Reusability*.

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Introduction

The metadata schema originally used in the RADx Data Hub exhibits several limitations. In the data file metadata schema, key limitations included insufficient metadata coverage, numerous unpopulated fields, and an inefficient structural design. For the study metadata schema, there was no documented and publicly accessible schema available, limiting consistency and reusability.

The updated data file schema addresses these limitations by expanding metadata coverage and restructuring the template for clarity and efficiency. New elements now capture sample-level properties, variable-level statistics, and file-level attributes to enhance interpretability and machine-actionability. Unused elements have been removed, and the schema has been streamlined by flattening single-instance fields. The previously separate “creator” and “contributor” elements are merged into a “Contributors” section, with roles specified via controlled vocabularies. The updated schema also differentiates between individual and organizational contributors, providing tailored fields for each. Additionally, a standardized, publicly accessible study metadata schema has been implemented to ensure consistent, FAIR-aligned documentation at the study level.

Limitations of Original Metadata Schemas

The original schemas, while functional and effective in capturing essential metadata, exhibited several limitations. The following sections detail these limitations as observed in both the data file metadata schema and the study metadata schema.

Limitations of Data File Metadata Schema

Inadequate Metadata Coverage

The original data file metadata schema in the RADx Data Hub established a solid foundation by capturing essential file-level metadata such as file name and parent study. However, opportunities remain to strengthen their ability to convey deeper contextual and structural information. The original schema did not include

variable-level descriptions, or related files, which limits the metadata's ability to fully represent the content and intended use of the data files on its own. Additionally, technical characteristics of CSV files, such as row and column counts, header presence, delimiter type, and encoding, were not captured, making automated parsing and interpretation more challenging.

Excessive and Unused Metadata Fields

The original metadata schema was designed with rich metadata fields. However, 58 of these fields have remained consistently unpopulated. This presents an opportunity to refine the schema by aligning it more closely with actual usage patterns and contributor needs. Streamlining underutilized fields can help simplify the metadata entry process, reduce contributor burden, and enhance the overall usability and efficiency of metadata submission.

Inefficiencies in Metadata Structure Design

The original metadata schema used a nested structural design in which all fields were encapsulated within elements. This approach was well-suited for metadata elements requiring multiple instances. However, it introduced unnecessary complexity when applied to fields intended for single-instance use. As shown in Figure 1, elements marked with "(0 .. ∞)", such as Data File Titles and Data File Subjects, supported multiple instances. In contrast, elements without this notation, like Data File Identity and Data File Language, were intended for single-instance use.

Data File Titles (0 .. ∞) ?	▼
Data File Identity ?	▼
Data File Language ?	▼
Data File Subjects (0 .. ∞) ?	▼
Data File Descriptions (0 .. ∞) ?	▼
Data File Data Dictionary ?	▼
Data File Creators (0 .. ∞) ?	▼
Data File Related Resources (0 .. ∞) ?	▼
Data File Contributors (0 .. ∞) ?	▼
Data File Rights (0 .. ∞) ?	▼
Data File Dates (0 .. ∞) ?	▼
Data File Parent Studies (0 .. ∞) ?	▼
Data File Funding Sources (0 .. ∞) ?	▼
Data File Distributions (0 .. ∞) ?	▼
Data Characteristics Summary ?	▼
Data Sources (0 .. ∞) ?	▼
Data Streams (0 .. ∞) ?	▼
Data File Creation Processes (0 .. ∞) ?	▼
Data File Temporal Coverage (0 .. ∞) ?	▼
Data File Spatial Coverage (0 .. ∞) ?	▼
Data File Elevation Coverage (0 .. ∞) ?	▼
Auxiliary Metadata ?	▼

Figure 1. Collapsed View of Original Data File Metadata Schema.

Additionally, the original data file metadata schema distinguished between “Data File Contributors” and “Data File Creators” to reflect different roles. However, both elements ultimately contained identical subfields and differed only in name. Since a creator is inherently a specific type of contributor, maintaining them as separate elements introduced redundancy and added complexity to the schema without providing additional informational value.

In addition, the schema applied a uniform structure to all contributor instances, requiring the same set of fields regardless of whether the contributor was an individual or an organization. As a result, organizational entries were expected to include person-specific fields such as “Given Name” and “Family Name,” which were not applicable. This absence of structural differentiation led to confusion during metadata entry, resulting in occasional field misuse or omission and reducing overall clarity and consistency.

Limitations of Study Metadata Schema

Lack of a Defined and Publicly Accessible Study Metadata Schema

In contrast to the data file metadata, the RADx Data Hub lacks a documented and publicly accessible schema for study-level metadata. For the study metadata to support FAIR data principles, particularly interoperability and reusability, it must be defined by a well-structured, publicly available schema that is machine-readable, human-interpretable, and consistently applied. Developing and publishing such a schema is critical for advancing metadata quality and supporting scalable, standardized study metadata.

Updated Metadata Schemas

The updated metadata schemas introduce a series of targeted enhancements aimed at improving completeness, clarity, and usability. The following subsections describe specific updates to the data file metadata schema and the study metadata schema.

Data File Metadata Schema Updates and Extension

Additional Metadata

The updated data file metadata schema introduces additional fields to capture a broader and more informative range of attributes. New entries include sample-level characteristics such as reported age groups, races, and sexes, providing a clearer understanding of the dataset's population structure. It also captures variable-level descriptive statistics, including mean, median, and percentiles, which support more informed data assessment. Additionally, technical properties of CSV files, such as character encoding and column delimiters, are now recorded to aid in accurate parsing. References to related files, including origin and transform copies, further enhance contextual understanding and data traceability.

Remove Empty Metadata Elements

Elements that remained unpopulated across all studies in the RADx Data Hub have been permanently removed. This includes entire elements such as Data File Distributions, Data File Elevation Coverage, Data File Rights, Data File Spatial Coverage, Data File Temporal Coverage, Data Sources, and Data Streams, along with their associated fields. This reduction eliminates unnecessary complexity and enhances the metadata entry experience.

Refine Structure of Metadata Schema

The updated data file metadata schema introduces a streamlined schema that enhances clarity and usability by flattening single-instance fields previously buried in nested structures. These fields now appear at the top level of the schema, simplifying both user input and programmatic parsing. For example, as shown in Figure 2, fields like "Titles," previously nested within the "Data File Titles" element, are now flattened to the top level. In addition, the schema groups related fields into logical sections, improving readability and aligning with metadata modeling best practices.

File attributes ?

Titles ^{*} (0..∞) ?

No instances yet

File name ^{*} ?

File size in bytes ?

Number Only

SHA256 digest ?

Media type ?

Start typing to filter

Version ^{*} ?

Dates (0..∞) ?

Related files ?

Data dictionary file name ?

Harmonization status ?

Origcopy file name ?

Transformcopy file name ?

Linked data files (0..∞) ?

Figure 2. Flattened Metadata Fields Grouped into Sections.

The updated data file metadata schema also consolidates “Data File Creators” and “Data File Contributors” into a single “Contributors” section, thereby eliminating redundancy in metadata representation. As seen in Figure 3, creator instances that previously fell under “Data File Creators” can now be precisely designated as “Creator” through the controlled vocabulary used in the “Contributor Type” field. Additionally, contributors are now distinctly categorized as either individual or organizational instances, with customized subfields to capture relevant attributes for each type. This structural refinement reduces redundancy, improves precision, and supports more accurate metadata capture.

Contributors [?]

Organizational contributors (0 .. ∞) [?] + 📄 🗑️ ^

Organization name * [?]

Organization roles * (0 .. ∞) [?] No instances yet + 📄 🗑️

Organization email [?]

Organization ROR [?]

Organization UEI [?]

Individual contributors (0 .. ∞) [?] + 📄 🗑️ ^

Contributor roles (0 .. ∞) [?] No instances yet + 📄 🗑️

Contributor name * [?]

Contributor given name [?]

Contributor family name [?]

Contributor email [?]

Contributor ORCID [?]

contributorAffiliations (0 .. ∞) [?] No instances yet + 📄 🗑️ ^

Figure 3. Contributors Section in the Updated Data File Metadata Schema.

Study Metadata Schema Updates and Extension

A new study metadata schema has been created based on existing study metadata in the RADx Data Hub and is now posted in CEDAR. This formalized schema supports improved findability, sharing, and reuse by providing a standardized, structured framework for capturing study-level metadata.

Resources

1. Source of truth for the Data File Metadata Specification:

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1Kwe4PFodciXo-XDX2bHN8F-CRAMopguol9YKFX6piaQ/edit?gid=118145754#gid=118145754>

2. Data File Metadata Specification in CEDAR:

<https://openview.metadatascenter.org/templates/https:%2F%2Frepo.metadatascenter.org%2Ftemplates%2Fa4e68f79-f9c4-4481-8b09-b116f525d072>

3. Source of truth for the Study Metadata Specification:

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1mKhTYuXT7JBLWt2UbM9FRnFF7sT8l3FR49nPP4DYZGM/edit?gid=0#gid=0>

4. Study Metadata Specification in CEDAR:

<https://openview.metadatascenter.org/templates/https:%2F%2Frepo.metadatascenter.org%2Ftemplates%2F9ade43b0-ea0c-499d-ac65-4b624a3b9db4>